

**THE SIGNIFICANCE OF FORMING THE IDEA OF THE NATIONAL
IDEOLOGY IN THE MIND OF THE YOUTH**

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Abstract: In this article, the national idea and ideology is fully analyzed from the point of view of the era, and how much is necessary in the morals of our youth. According to him, it has been proven that ideology is necessary for the realization of any lofty goals, and a correctly chosen ideology can quickly and easily reach the desired goal.

Key words: National idea, ideology, culture, nationality, spirituality, ideological gap

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada milliy g'oya va mafkuraning davr nuqtayi nazaridan kelib chiqqan holda to'liq tahlil etilib yoshlarimiz axloqida nechog'lik zarur ekanligi keltirilib o'tilgan. Unga ko'ra har qanday yuksak maqsadlarni ro'yobga chiqarish uchun mafkura lozimligi, to'g'ri tanlangan mafkura esa ko'zlangan maqsad sari tez va oson eltishi isbotlab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Milliy g'oya, mafkura, madaniyat, milliylik, ma'naviyat, mafkuraviy bo'shliq

Аннотация: В этой статье национальная идея и идеология полностью анализируются с точки зрения эпохи, а также того, насколько это необходимо в нравственности нашей молодежи. По его словам, доказано, что идеология необходима для реализации любых высоких целей, а правильно выбранная идеология позволяет быстро и легко достичь желаемой цели.

Ключевые слова: Национальная идея, идеология, культура, национальность, духовность, идеологический разрыв

INTRODUCTION

In the period of development, it is necessary to harmonize national and universal values and apply them to the society. In the conditions of the development of social networks, various foreign ideas and moral disorders reflected in them have a negative impact on the minds of our youth, and it has become an urgent problem today. Based on this, the main goal of pedagogy is to inculcate concepts such as national pride, value, loyalty to the motherland, duty and responsibility, and to form moral qualities in them. Social customs are of particular importance in regulating and managing the behavior and actions of young people. Repetition of the examples of manners and morals characteristic of our nationality at home, in studies and in public places strengthens the intuition of young people and becomes a habit in them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Spirituality and ideology are strongly connected with each other. Spirituality is a person's psyche, self-awareness, and potential for striving for excellence, while the concept of "National Independence Idea: Basic Concepts and Principles" states that "Ideology is a specific social group, stratum, nation, state, it is a system of ideas that embodies the needs, goals, interests, dreams and aspirations of the people and society" [1].

The place of ideology in spirituality is that it embodies the aspirations, mentality and moods of a person, society, or nation or groups. Like spirituality, the role of ideology in the development of the state and society is extremely large. As the first President Islam Karimov noted, "Ideology is not only today, but also the most urgent political and social issue, it is a spiritual and spiritual force that unites any society towards healthy and noble goals and achieves its goals - has been a foundation that gives strength." [2] Ideology performs the following tasks in the development of society: firstly, it performs the tasks in the economic, social-political and spiritual-educational spheres of the state's development: firstly, it performs the tasks in the economic, social-political and spiritual-educational spheres of the state's development embodies;

Secondly, it serves to unite all citizens, different nationalities, peoples, classes and social groups towards one idea and goal on the scale of one state, one country; thirdly, it embodies the ideas of the internal and external policy of the state and promotes it to citizens; fourthly, it activates the creativity, creativity, and creativity of citizens living within the state and directs them to the goals of society; fifth, it expresses the people's hopes and dreams, mobilizes the entire society and citizens to solve the problems existing in the society; sixth, ideology forms certain political, economic, and spiritual-educational views in society.

DISCUSSION

It should be noted that Islam Karimov, the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, explained the role and importance of the national idea, national ideology in building a democratic society in Uzbekistan:

"Ideology is necessary in the life of any society. Without ideology, it is inevitable that a person, society, and state will lose their way. Secondly, wherever there is an ideological gap, a foreign ideology is destined to rule there." [3] Every person, a citizen of Uzbekistan, should understand this deeply and understand it. After all, if there is no solid and clear ideology, idea, goal of the society and the members of the society, it will face a crisis. States and societies have appeared in the history of mankind, and ideological views have been formed along with them. The reason is that the ideology of the state or society is like a person who takes a risk without any goal plan.

Have you set out - the address and destination should be clear. Islam Karimov, our first president, spoke about how important the national idea is in achieving the ambitious goals that every nation has set for itself.

In the book "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" he wrote the following: "The centuries-old history of humanity shows that every nation in this world that decides to build its own nation-state must fulfill its high tasks, unite people and mobilize to do, to inspire confidence in their hearts, to find additional strength and support in the transition from the old social system to a completely new system, the expression of a common, unified goal and desire considers the existing national idea as a support and

support"[4] . That is why the First President Islam Karimov has been paying special attention to the problem of the national idea and ideology since the first years of independence. Islam Karimov draws our attention to the fact that a vacuum cannot be allowed in the world of ideology on a regular basis, and that in the event of such a situation, there is no doubt that the empty space of ideology will try to occupy a place of ideas that are foreign to us and completely foreign to us. it is not for nothing that they have been drawing our attention again and again"[5].

RESULTS

Independence has given us bright opportunities for development. Our people live with great dreams and aspirations. A legal state, a just civil society is the bright destination before us. But these addresses are not acquired without hard work, research, creativity, and creative work. The new society requires a highly developed mind, spiritual maturity to rise to a higher level. Our national independence ideology enriched with advanced democratic rules and concepts is one of the decisive criteria of this new spirituality. Because "National Independence Ideology of the Society of Uzbekistan, in its essence, represents the main goals and objectives of our nation, connects its past and future, and serves to realize its centuries-old dreams and aspirations. system"[6] .

Therefore, it will be possible to realize the great tasks of the development of our country and people only if we can deeply grasp the ideology of national independence, only if it becomes an integral part of our worldview, if it takes a firm place in our hearts. Spirituality cannot develop without ideology. Because ideology is of great importance as a driving force in shaping the human spirit, restoring national values and realizing the goals of society.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, I can say that awareness of national identity plays an important role in the development of our country, national consciousness is an invaluable internal factor in raising the feeling of love for our country and raising a perfect person. Understanding national identity, finding human identity begins with studying history.

A nation that has not mastered the historical experience of its national statehood, national culture and spiritual development is not capable of national revival.

There are two most important directions in the way of building a new Uzbekistan with citizens with a new and broad outlook: firstly, by increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work, the idea of "national revival - national rise" is fully integrated into the life of society. implementation, therefore, the formation of ideological immunity and information analysis skills in the population, especially young people, against various forms of ideological threats and information attacks are urgent tasks is included.

Secondly, to ensure economic stability while increasing the well-being of the population, in this, first of all, to increase the volume of local production, to create an added value chain, to launch new capacities that operate at higher levels, to create a favorable business environment for attracting foreign investments and investment. is to join the leading economically developed countries by increasing attractiveness. Revival of work in these two directions plays an important role in ensuring high morale and development. As the President noted, "If the economy is the body of society's life, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values.

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